

cultures was made on a detached stem. Inoculated tissues were discolored from light to dark brown. Four days after pot-grown plants of IR8 were inoculated at the maximum tillering stage, symptoms began to appear. A lesion extended upward and downward from the inoculation point; the leaf sheath became

brown. But the lesion was restricted only to the inoculated internodes in which the stem tissues as well as the leaf sheath became rotten and discolored. The outer leaves of infected plants senesced rapidly.

Initial bacteriological studies indicated that the causal bacterium may be similar to that which causes "bacterium bruzone

disease" of rice in Hungary or "sheath brown rot" of rice in Japan. According to Goto, the pathogen was closely related to *Pseudomonas marginalis*, but different from the "sheath rot" caused by a strain of *Erwinia carotovora* in Indonesia in 1964. The etiology and identification of the bacterium are being studied. ■

Occurrence of rice ragged stunt disease in West Bengal, India

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In the 1978 wet season, natural infection of rice ragged stunt disease was observed

on Jaya in a trial plot of the Rice Production Training Institute farm. About 50% of the rice hills were affected. The population of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* was low at the time. Scattered diseased plants were later found in isolated pockets in the region. This is the first report of ragged stunt in

West Bengal. The primary symptoms of the disease observed were stunting (photo 1), vein-swelling on ragged leaves (photo 2), distorted twisting of the flag leaf, and incomplete emergence of the panicle (photo 3).

1. Healthy plant (right) and stunted plant (left) infected with ragged stunt disease.

2. Vein-swelling on ragged leaves.

3. Incomplete emergence of panicle and twisted flag leaf.

Serological studies of rice ragged stunt virus

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Crude or partially purified material containing B-spiked subviral particles (SVP) of rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV) from diseased plants (mailed to Italy from the Philippines) was injected into rabbits for antiserum production. When tested by the gel diffusion method, the antiserum had a titer of 1/16 against healthy rice material, and at least 1/64 against RRSV preparations. When the antiserum was tested by immunoelectron microscopy using the decoration technique, specific antibody halos around

SVP of RRSV were detected up to a dilution of 1/256. Preparations of SVP of maize rough dwarf virus (MRDV), oat sterile dwarf virus (OSDV), and pangola stunt virus (PSV) were not decorated by the RRSV antiserum. Likewise, the antisera of MRDV, OSDV, PSV, and sugarcane Fiji disease virus failed to decorate SVP of RRSV. Thus, RRSV is not serologically related to those viruses that make up the fijiviruses group, but might be a new member of a plant reovirus group having affinities with the fijiviruses. Furthermore, the antiserum reacted positively to diseased materials collected in India, Indonesia, Philippines, and Thailand. Hence, in addition to being similar in symptomatology and transmission, the RRSV in those countries are serologically related.

Effect of nitrogen on lesion development in rice resistant to bacterial blight

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It is generally believed that increases in nitrogen fertilizer increase bacterial blight infection. If rices with different resistance genes and pathotypes with specific virulence are identified, then scientists can evaluate interactions among nitrogen fertilizer and those factors. Initial greenhouse experiments showed that the lesion length on varieties with intermediate (moderate or partial) resistance, such as Pulo and Sailboro 302, increased with increased nitrogen level. But the total lesion length was considerably less than that on rices with

no functional resistance (IR8 and TN1). When rices with adult plant resistance (IR1698 and IR944) were infected at tillering stage (45 days after seeding), lesion length did not differ from that on rices (IR8) with no resistance to pathotypes 1 and 2. High nitrogen levels did not affect lesion length on varieties

with specific resistance. But lesion length increased if the variety-pathotype combination was compatible (i.e. the varieties' resistance was overcome by pathotypes of different virulence). Thus, when IR20 was infected with pathotype 1 (to which it is resistant), lesion length did not significantly increase. But when

infection was caused by Pathotype 2 (to which IR20 is susceptible), lesion length increased proportionally with increased nitrogen. When IR1545-339 was infected with both pathotypes (to which the breeding line was resistant), lesion length did not increase. ■

Effect of fungicides on the inactivation of sclerotia and mycelia of *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Sheath blight disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is severe in many rice-growing areas of Tamil Nadu. The effect of certain fungicides on the viability of sclerotia and mycelia of *R. solani* was studied.

Soil was well sieved and air-dried, then placed in 25-ml vials and autoclaved for 1 hour at 15 lb. An 8-mm agar disc of the pathogen was placed on the soil and then covered with 2.5 cm sterilized soil. Similarly sclerotia were placed on the soil surface of another set of vials and covered with soil.

The fungicides Bavistin, Benlate, Demosan, Hinosan, wettable Ceresan, Brassicol, Kitazin, Vitavax, and thiabendazole were tested at 0.05, 0.1, and 0.2% levels. Five milliliters of each fungicidal solution was applied to the soil surface with a pipette. The vials were incubated for 24 hours at room temperature. Then they were emptied and the soil was washed off with running water. The mycelial discs and sclerotia were removed with sterile forceps, plated on Czapek's agar medium, and observed for viability.

All the fungicides except wettable Ceresan completely inhibited mycelial growth at all the concentrations. Hinosan, Kitazin, and Vitavax completely inhibited sclerotial germination at all concentrations. Bavistin at 0.2% inhibited sclerotial germination. Benlate, Demosan, Brassicol, thiabendazole, and wettable Ceresan did not effectively inhibit sclerotial germination. ■

In vitro* effect of certain fungicides on the growth and sclerotial production of *Rhizoctonia solani

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Sheath blight disease of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is serious in Tamilnadu. The efficacy of certain fungicides against *R. solani* was tested. The fungicides EL-273, N.F. 48, Bavistin, Vitavax, Difolatan, Agallol, Plantvax, Benlate, Agrosan GN, Fytolan, Brestan, Brassicol, thiabendazole, Hinosan, Kitazin, Daconil, Demosan, Macuprax, wettable Ceresan, Dithane D-14, Dithane M-45, Dexon, captan, thiram, and Dithane Z-78 were

incorporated in Czapek's medium at 0.025%, 0.05%, 0.1%, and 0.2% levels. The medium was seeded with *R. solani*. After 15 days of incubation the dry weight of the fungus was determined.

All of the fungicides tested inhibited the pathogen growth at all concentrations. The fungicides N.F. 48, Bavistin, Vitavax, Benlate, Brassicol, thiabendazole, Hinosan, Kitazin, Daconil, and Demosan completely arrested growth and sclerotial production, even at 0.025%. On the other hand, Agallol, EL-273, Agrosan, Dexon, captan, and thiram completely inhibited the growth and sclerotial production of the pathogen only at the 0.2% level. The other fungicides decreased growth as concentration was increased. ■

Root injury and kresek development on rice

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In the field, kresek infection on rice plants usually occurs 1 to 6 weeks after transplanting. An early study suggested that root injury is related to kresek infection. In this study, kresek developed on seedlings raised in a seedbed infested with bacterial cells of *Xanthomonas oryzae*. The percentage of kresek was high when the seedbox was infested near transplanting time, but was minimal when the seedbed was infested at the time of sowing and the seedlings were transplanted 21 days later.

More kresek was produced in transplanted than in direct-seeded rice when the seedbox soil was infested with the bacterial pathogen by incorporating bacterial suspension at different concentrations. The percentage of kresek

infection and inoculum dosages were linearly correlated in transplanted rice.

Two types of seedbeds were compared. In the ordinary seedbed, kresek incidence was similar regardless of whether the roots of seedlings were injured by clipping or not. Among seedlings raised in the dapog bed, those with uninjured roots had considerably less kresek infection than those with injured roots. ■

Seed pathology of rice in Indonesia, 1975-78

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The fungi incidence was analyzed in 133 seed samples of rice from Java, Bali, and South Sulawesi (Indonesia) from 1975 to 1978. The samples were obtained from 13 commercial and 40 local varieties or promising lines. Fifteen fungal genera and